

Appendix S1. Extended breeding design showing the crosses within the first maternal group.

Figure S1: A pedigree showing how a portion of the experimental generation (F₃) was produced and derived from the initial population (P) collected from Québec in 2008. **This pedigree shows the crosses within the first maternal group (M₁), coloured in turquoise.** Unlike the second maternal group, this maternal group does not contain 1st cousin relationships for estimating components of dominance.